

Exploring functionalized nanocrystalline cellulose binders for potassium-ion batteries

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Abstract

The development of sustainable and efficient binder materials is crucial to improve the performance and environmental compatibility of potassium-ion batteries (KIBs). In this study, we investigate the use of cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) as eco-friendly binders for carbon-based anodes for KIBs. Three types of CNCs were synthesized from microcrystalline cellulose via enzymatic, hydrochloric acid, and sulfuric acid hydrolysis, and fully characterized by ATR-FTIR, elemental analysis, XRD, and FE-SEM. Their electrochemical stability was confirmed by cyclic voltammetry on binder-only electrodes, which showed negligible activity in the 0.01–3 V vs. K⁺/K window. When incorporated as binders into anode electrodes with commercial Super C45 carbon, CNCs enabled excellent electrochemical performance, outperforming conventional carboxymethyl cellulose binders. Among them, the cellulose nanocrystals synthesized from enzymatic hydrolysis provided the best results in terms of specific capacity, capacity retention (97% after 100 cycles), rate capability, and electrode morphology. These improvements are attributed to its neutral surface chemistry and enhanced structural homogeneity. Our findings highlight CNCs as promising, low-cost, and sustainable binder materials for next-generation KIB systems.

Introduction

It is well known that Li-ion batteries (LIBs) have taken the lead as portable energy storage devices over the past few decades [1]. However, in many applications—particularly in large-scale energy storage systems where high energy density is not the primary requirement—alternative technologies

that are more sustainable and cost-effective are being actively explored. In this context, potassium-ion batteries (KIBs) have gained considerable attention due to several advantages that make them competitive with LIBs [2]. One key benefit of implementing potassium in batteries is its abundance in the Earth's crust (2.09 wt% K vs. 0.0017 wt% for Li) and its homogeneous global distribution, making it a significantly cheaper and more accessible resource [3]. Additionally, potassium exhibits a low standard reduction potential (-2.93 V vs. SHE), which is the closest to lithium (-3.04 V) [4]. Furthermore, the weak Lewis acidity of potassium results in smaller solvated ion size, enhancing their diffusion rate and facilitating ion transport across the electrode/electrolyte interface [5], [6]. Despite these advantages, the larger size of desolvated potassium ions ($d_{K^+} = 1.38$ Å) compared to lithium ($d_{Li^+} = 0.76$ Å) represents a critical challenge [2]. The substantial volume changes associated with the potassiation/depotassiation processes can lead to mechanical stress, electrode cracking, and, ultimately, rapid capacity fading [7].

To address these issues, the development of more effective binder materials has become increasingly important in enhancing the electrochemical performance and durability of KIB electrodes [8], [9]. Binders play a key role in battery electrodes by holding together the different components of the electrodes without interfering with the electrochemical reactions occurring during the charge/discharge processes [10]. To achieve this, they must be electrochemically stable within the working potential window, elastic enough to tolerate the significant volume changes that particularly affect this type of system and provide strong adhesion to the current collectors to facilitate the exchange of electric charge with the external circuit [11]. Currently, one of the most widely used binders in this area is poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), which meets many of these criteria and has been the binder of choice in most commercial battery systems. However, PVDF presents several drawbacks. Most notably, its processing requires the use of *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), a toxic and costly organic solvent. Other disadvantages include its high production costs and challenges related to recyclability and environmental impact [11]. That is why different alternatives are being studied to replace PVDF for more sustainable and inexpensive materials [12].

In the above scenario, cellulose materials can be considered promising, safe, and sustainable alternatives to traditional binders, thanks to their abundance, thermal stability, good mechanical properties, hydrophilic character, and, not least, their economic convenience [13], [14]. This hydrophilic biopolymer is essential in the structure of plant cell walls and is also present in fungi, invertebrates, and some marine creatures, among others [15]. As a consequence, cellulose is an abundant material that can be obtained from renewable resources and, thus, it is biodegradable and safe for human health. Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) represent the crystalline regions within cellulose fibrils and can be produced by applying chemical processes to isolate these crystalline domains by a

top-down approach. They typically display a diameter in the range between 5 and 50 nm and a length ranging from 100 to 500 nm [16]. Nanostructured cellulose, indeed, could ensure a better mobility of ions thanks to the high specific surface area, with respect to other forms of cellulose. Diverse kinds of hydrolytic reactions produce nanocrystals with different surface or crystalline properties: hydrochloric acid hydrolysis yields neutral nanocrystals (N-CNC), composed by pure cellulose, whose surface is constituted by free hydroxyl groups [17]; sulfuric acid hydrolysis produces functionalized nanocrystals in which primary hydroxyl groups are randomly sulfated (S-CNC) [18]. Given the toxicity and hazardousness of acids, the milder enzymatic hydrolysis with endoglucanases represents an effective alternative to prepare neutral nanocrystals (eN-CNC) avoiding the release of concentrated acid as a waste [19]. CNC have been a popular choice for functional materials applications in a variety of fields—including biomedical applications [20], paper manufacture [21], and energy storage devices [22]—due to their flexibility, low density, and exceptional rheological properties [23]. These properties are largely attributed to the hydrogen-bonded crystalline network formed by primary and secondary hydroxyl (OH) groups on their surfaces [24]. These OH groups not only promote structural organization through electrostatic interactions, but also offer chemical versatility, enabling functional modifications to tailor CNC properties [25].

Despite the promising features of CNCs, their potential as binder materials in advanced battery systems—such as potassium-ion batteries—remains largely unexplored. In this work, we synthesize and characterize three types of CNCs produced via different hydrolysis methods, and evaluate their performance as binders in carbon-based anodes for KIBs through various electrochemical techniques. A key aspect influencing their behavior is their dispersibility in polar solvents, which varies depending on their surface chemistry. Sulfated CNCs (S-CNC) are more easily dispersed in polar solvents due to the surface charge repulsion of negative charges formed at $\text{pH} > 1$. In contrast, neutral CNCs (N-CNC and eN-CNC), lacking surface charges, tend to aggregate in aqueous suspension, which limits their widespread use and commercial availability [26]. To overcome this limitation, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was selected as an effective dispersing medium for all CNC types. Thanks to its hydrogen bond-accepting nature, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) facilitates the separation of individual nanocrystals and promotes the formation of stable gels, even in the case of neutral CNCs. Finally, to contextualize our findings, we compare the electrochemical behavior of CNC-based electrodes with those fabricated using carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), one of the most widely used cellulose-derived binders.

Materials and methods

Materials and synthesis

Avicel PH-101 was purchased from Sigma Aldrich and was used as the starting material for nanocrystalline cellulose isolation. Dialysis was carried out at room temperature against deionized water in nitrocellulose tubes with a cut-off of 12600 Da. Hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, and DMSO were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were purchased from Fluka. Endoglucanase from *Aspergillus niger* (1,4-(1,3:1,4)- β -D-glucan 4-glucan-hydrolase, EC3.2.1.2) was purchased from MP Biomedicals. Super C45 carbon black was purchased from Imerys, Timcal. CMC 2200, potassium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (KFSI), ethylene carbonate (EC), and diethyl carbonate (DEC) were purchased from DAICEL, BLDpharm and Merck, respectively.

N-CNC

To synthesize the neutral nanocrystals, 75 mL of deionized water was introduced in a 250 mL three-necked round-bottomed flask equipped with a water condenser and a mechanical stirrer. Then, the flask was cooled in an ice bath and 75 mL of concentrated HCl was added. After that, 7.50 g of Avicel PH-101 was added and the suspension was warmed to 105 °C for 6 h. The system was cooled to room temperature and diluted with 75 mL of distilled water and the mixture was transferred to polypropylene centrifugation tubes. Centrifugation at 4000 rpm was repeated four times, replacing the supernatant liquid with fresh deionized water until the pH was approximately 3. Then, the precipitate was suspended in deionized water with the aid of a Dr. Hielscher sonicator equipped with an ultrasonic horn with a 3.5 mm diameter (micro-tip) operated in pulsed mode, with a power of 40 W, and 0.6 s pulses for 10 min and dialyzed against distilled water until neutrality using a cellulose nitrate membrane with a molecular weight cut-off of 12400 Da. The resulting suspension was transferred to polypropylene centrifugation tubes and centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant suspension was lyophilized, yielding 1.54 g of CNCs (21% yield)

eN-CNC

Avicel pretreatment required the use of a ball mill with horizontal oscillation (BM500, Anton Paar) equipped with two 50 mL stainless steel jars and one 2.5 cm diameter ball for each jar. Each jar was loaded with 5 g of Avicel. The pretreatment was performed with a frequency of 3 Hz for 50 minutes without breaks. 5.04 g of ball-milled Avicel was added to 50 mL of 50 mM phosphate buffer pH = 5.0 and homogenized with a tissue master. Then, *Aspergillus niger* endoglucanase (enzyme:cellulose =1:10 ratio) was introduced into the suspension. The reaction mixture was shaken in an orbital shaker at 55 °C for 96 h at 150 rpm. After the incubation period, the reaction was transferred to a beaker and heated from 55 °C to 95 °C for 15 min to inactivate the enzyme. The resulting mixture was subjected to centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes. This was followed by a washing step with 20 mL of 0.1 M HCl, followed by another centrifugation cycle at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes. To remove the HCl, the solution was subjected to multiple centrifugations with deionized H₂O (20 mL) at 4000 rpm for

10 minutes, discarding the supernatant each time, until neutrality was confirmed with litmus paper. Once neutral pH was reached, the suspension was subjected to a 24-hour dialysis using a cellulose nitrate membrane with a molecular weight cut-off of 12400 Da. Next, the suspension was subjected to sonication with a 400 W Dr. Hielscher sonicator with a power of 40 W and pulses of 0.6 seconds, for 10 minutes. A final centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 10 min was conducted, and the supernatant containing nanocrystals was collected and lyophilized. The material was isolated in 76% yield.

S-CNC

In order to obtain the sulfated cellulose nanocrystals, 250 mL of deionized water was introduced in a 1L cylindrical reactor equipped with a water condenser and a mechanical stirrer. Then, the flask was cooled in an ice bath, and 250 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added. After that, 30 g of Avicel PH-101 was added, and the suspension was warmed to 45 °C for 80 min. The system was cooled to room temperature, diluted with deionized water (250 mL) and the mixture was transferred to polypropylene centrifugation tubes. Centrifugation at 4000 rpm was repeated, replacing the supernatant liquid with fresh deionized water until the pH was approximately 1. Then, the precipitate was suspended in deionized water with the aid of a Dr Hielsher tip sonicator equipped with an ultrasonic horn with a 3.5 mm diameter (micro-tip) operated in pulsed mode, with a power of 40 W, 0.6 s pulses for 10 min, and dialyzed against distilled water until neutrality using a cellulose nitrate membrane with a molecular weight cut-off of 12400 Da. The resulting suspension was transferred to polypropylene centrifugation tubes and centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant suspension was lyophilized, yielding 4.63 g of CNCs (15% yield).

Gel preparation

For each sample, 30 mg of CNCs were added to 5 mL of DMSO. The suspension was sonicated with a Dr Hielsher tip sonicator equipped with an ultrasonic horn with a 3.5 mm diameter tip (micro-tip) operated in pulsed mode, with a power of 320 W, 0.8 s pulses. The gelation process took about 15 minutes for each sample.

Materials characterizations

Elemental analyses were performed on an Elementar Vario Micro Cube analyzer. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and sulfur contents were determined. All analyses were carried out on 5 mg of dry samples to evidence changes in sulfur or nitrogen content. Oxygen content was calculated for all samples by the difference. All determinations were done in duplicate.

Attenuated total reflectance – Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectra were collected on a Thermo Fischer Nicolet iS50 FTIR instrument interfaced with an ATR ITX accessory equipped with a diamond crystal (radiation penetration approximately 2 μm at 1000 cm⁻¹). The spectra were recorded at room temperature in air in the range between 4000 and 650 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, 16

accumulated scans, and a DTGS as a detector. The spectra were elaborated using the software SPECTRA.

Field emission – scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) analyses were carried out on a FEI FEG-Quanta 450 instrument. Cellulose nanocrystals were deposited on glass from a DMSO suspension at a concentration of 1 mg/L. For the deposition, 20 μL of the suspension were cast on a round microscopy glass with 12 mm diameter. After two minutes, the drop was wiped off with a piece of clean filter paper. The sample was left to dry on air and then stored in a desiccator until the moment of the analysis. Samples were coated with platinum (5 nm) before analysis.

High-resolution synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) and total scattering measurements were performed at beamline ID31 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF). The sample powders were loaded into cylindrical slots (approx. 1 mm thickness) held between Kapton windows in a high-throughput sample holder. Each sample was measured in transmission geometry with an incident X-ray energy of 75.051 keV ($\lambda = 0.16520 \text{ \AA}$). Measured intensities were collected using a Pilatus CdTe 2M detector (1679 \times 1475 pixels, 172 \times 172 μm^2 each) positioned with the incident beam in the corner of the detector. The sample-to-detector distance was approximately 1.5 m for the high-resolution measurements and 0.3 m for the total scattering measurements. Background measurements for the empty windows were measured and subtracted. NIST SRM 660b (LaB6) was used for geometry calibration performed with the software pyFAI followed by image integration including a flat-field, geometry, solid-angle, and polarization corrections. The 2theta axis was normalized with the respective wavelength to obtain an absolute axis on momentum transfer Q , where $Q = 4\pi \frac{\sin \theta}{\lambda}$.

Electrodes preparation and characterization

Electrochemical characterizations were performed in two different electrode configurations to evaluate both the binders alone (binder electrodes) and commercial Super C45 carbon combined with each binder (C45/binder electrodes). The binder electrodes were prepared by mixing each CNC material with DMSO at a concentration of 30 mg/mL. The resulting gels were coated onto aluminium foil using a doctor blade with a wet controlled thickness of 100 μm . The coated films were dried in an oven at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h and then punched into 10 mm disks. Additionally, bare aluminum foil was cut into disks, used as control electrodes for comparative analysis. All electrodes were subsequently dried under vacuum at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h in a Büchi oven.

Similarly, the C45/binder electrodes were prepared by mixing 80 wt% of Super C45 carbon and 20 wt% per each binder material, using DMSO as a solvent. The mixture was subjected to ball milling at 30 Hz for 20 min, and the resulting slurry was coated onto aluminium foil using a doctor blade at a wet thickness of 100 μm . After drying at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h, the electrodes were punched into 15 mm disks and subjected to vacuum drying at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h in a Büchi oven. For comparative analysis,

additional electrodes were prepared using CMC as the binder, following the same procedure, but employing deionized water as solvent.

Cell assembly was performed in an argon-filled glove box (MBRAUN MB10 compact, $O_2 < 0.5$ ppm, $H_2O < 0.5$ ppm) in two different configurations: a three-electrode T-cell was used to characterize the binder electrodes, while a half-cell configuration in LIR2032 coin cell was used to test the C45/binder electrodes. Metallic potassium was used as both the counter and reference electrode, Whatman glass fiber disks were used as separators, and a 1 M solution of KFSI in EC:DEC (1:1, v:v) was used as the electrolyte.

Galvanostatic cycling (GC) of the C45/binder electrodes were conducted using an Arbin LBT-21084C battery tester within a potential range of 0.01–3.00 V vs. K^+/K , at a constant current density of 0.05 A/g over 100 cycles. To evaluate rate performance, after 20 cycles at 0.05 A/g, the current density was successively increased to 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.0, and 2.5 A/g, with 10 cycles at each rate, followed by 20 final cycles at 0.05 A/g. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were performed using a VSP-3e Biologic potentiostat/galvanostat within the same voltage window as GC, at a constant scan rate of 0.1 mV/s. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was conducted using a Biologic BCS-805, within a frequency range of 10 kHz to 20 mHz, applying a potential amplitude of 10 mV. EIS measurements were conducted intermittently during GC at different cycle numbers. The surface morphology of the pristine C45/binder electrodes was analysed using FESEM with an Auriga dual-beam FIB-SEM workstation (Zeiss).

Results and discussion

CNCs synthesis and characterization

The three typologies of nanocrystals under investigation were prepared from Avicel PH101. **Figure 1** schematically represents the preparation of the three cellulose nanocrystals typologies from the cellulose source. S-CNCs were prepared by sulfuric acid hydrolysis. This approach utilizes 64% sulfuric acid in water at moderate temperatures (i.e., 45 °C) and typically produces the desired nanostructured materials in low yield (15% for the reaction batch used in this work) [19], [27]. Neutral cellulose nanocrystals, instead, can be produced either by hydrochloric acid hydrolysis (giving N-CNC) [17], or mechano-enzymatic hydrolysis (obtaining eN-CNC) [19]. Hydrochloric acid hydrolysis requires higher temperature (i.e., 105 °C) and 6 hours of reaction time. Depending on the batch, also this method can give unsatisfactory results in terms of reaction yield (21% for the batch used in this work). Conversely, the mechano-enzymatic hydrolysis represents an interesting approach to the preparation of cellulose nanostructures, since it avoids the use of concentrated mineral acids and disposal of toxic or corrosive waste as in the previous two cases, and yields more reproducible results. For mechano-enzymatic hydrolysis, the endoglucanase from *Aspergillus niger* is

used to catalyze the hydrolysis reaction in a phosphate buffer at pH 5.0 as dispersing medium. To favor enzyme access to cellulose fibers, a mild mechanic pretreatment is applied to Avicel before the hydrolysis reaction, using a horizontal ball mill equipped with stainless steel jars.

Figure 1. Synthesis of cellulose nanocrystals from Avicel by different hydrolytic approaches.

Nanocrystals were characterized by elemental analyses: ATR-FTIR, FE-SEM, and XRD spectroscopy. **Table 1** collects the elemental analysis results of the three samples, in which the carbon content is in line with the expected content. Indeed, the lower carbon percentage found in each sample with respect to the theoretical cellulose value (44.45%) is due to the crystallized water content naturally present in the cellulose nanocrystals. As expected, the sulfur content in S-CNC is higher than in neutral CNCs. We calculated a degree of substitution with sulfate groups in S-CNC of ~ 0.03 , according to a previously described procedure [28]. The enzymatic CNCs, instead, present 0.25% of nitrogen content, due to the presence of traces of enzyme in the purified material (on average $\sim 2.5\%$ of total weight of eN-CNC, based on average aminoacid molecular weight).

Table 1. Elemental analyses results of the three CNCs samples. ^(a) Determination of oxygen weight percentage was done by difference.

	Elemental analysis (% w/w)					Cristallinity index
	C	H	N	S	O ^(a)	
N-CNC	40.81	6.12	0	0.02	53.05	76.3%
eN-CNC	41.03	6.13	0.25	0.04	52.55	76.9%
S-CNC	40.11	6.55	0	0.6	52.74	80.0%

ATR-FTIR spectra of the three compounds are reported in **Figure 2**. No significant difference could be noticed between the samples. In every case, the characteristic cellulose peaks are evident, such as the stretching of O-H at 3325 cm^{-1} , and the C-OH stretch at 1025 cm^{-1} . Furthermore, a weak signal of the deformation mode of anomeric CH is evident at 896 cm^{-1} . The signal of the bending mode of crystallized water in each sample falls at 1646 cm^{-1} . No evident signal of protein residue presence in eN-CNC could be detected by this spectroscopic technique.

Figure 2. ATR-FTIR spectra of neutral cellulose nanocrystals obtained by acid and enzymatic hydrolysis, respectively, in orange and green lines, and sulfated cellulose nanocrystals in violet line.

Figure 3. Diffractogram of N-CNC (in orange) eN-CNC (in green), and S-CNC (in violet).

Crystallinity indexes of cellulose nanocrystals are included in **Table 1**. The XRD pattern of the three samples are reported in **Figure 3**. The distinctive peaks of the diffractogram corresponding to cellulose I, the crystalline allomorph of cellulose found in plants, were identified in each sample. Diffraction patterns are plotted against an absolute axis on momentum transfer Q . Crystallinities were calculated from XRD pattern by the Segal method, considering the ratio $CrI = I_{200} - I_{am} / I_{200}$, where I_{200} represents the maximum intensity of the peak with Miller's indexes 200 (centered at $1.6Q$ in our spectra, and corresponding to 22.6° in the 2θ axis when CuK α 1 radiation is used), while the intensity of the amorphous peak is found at $1.3Q$ for cellulose I. The higher crystallinity found for S-CNC (i.e., 80.0%) reflects the efficiency of sulfuric acid in digesting amorphous cellulose regions. However, the other two samples have very close crystallinity values and reveal the feasibility of using neutral cellulose nanocrystals in several applications, especially considering the high yield obtained in the case of mechano-enzymatic hydrolysis.

Figure 4 collects the FE-SEM images of nanocrystals deposited from 1 mg/L suspensions in DMSO. In all cases, the morphology of the materials is in line with the expected dimension of cellulose nanocrystals (approximately 100 nm long). It is evident that the aggregation behaviour of the three typologies of nanocrystals, tending in all cases to form aggregates interacting by their long side, with neutral CNCs (both acid and enzymatic) tending to form nanocrystal clusters rather than thin films, as in the case of S-CNC.

Figure 4. SEM-micrographies of: a) N-CNC; b) eN-CNC; c) S-CNC, acquired on samples deposited on glass from 1 mg/L DMSO suspensions.

Binders electrochemical stability

In order to evaluate the electrochemical stability of the synthesized binders, CVs were carried out in the potential range of 0.01–3V vs K⁺/K. The voltammograms corresponding to cycles 1 to 5 of the CNC binders electrodes are shown in **Figure 5**. For the sake of comparison, the same protocol was adopted for T-cell with bare aluminum electrode. As observed, all CNC-based binders exhibited

remarkable stability within the working potential window. The CV curves of the CNC binders are very similar to each other, with no significant redox processes detected after the first cycle. During this cycle, a reduction peak is centered around 0.65 V, which is associated with the formation of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) products [29]. Indeed, this peak is also present in the voltammogram of the bare Al electrode (Figure 5d), indicating that it is not related to any irreversible reactions of the binders rather than of liquid electrolyte. After the first cycle, the CV curves stabilize and nearly overlap in subsequent cycles, indicating the stability of the synthesized binders. It is also worth noting that all three binder electrodes had equal mass loadings (but higher than the bare Al electrode). Despite this, the current intensity in all voltammograms remained very low and nearly identical across the four cells. This confirms that the binders are not electrochemically active within the explored potential window. Furthermore, it indicates that they do not catalyze electrolyte decomposition or contribute to side reactions, as long as they are not in contact with the carbon black. A more detailed evaluation of their behavior in composite carbon electrodes will be discussed in the following sections.

Figure 5. CV voltammograms at 0.1 mV/s of binder electrodes: (a) eN-CNC, (b) N-CNC, (c) S-CNC; and (d) bare aluminum.

Electrochemical evaluation and morphological characterization of C45/Binder electrodes

To study the electrochemical performance of the synthesized CNC as binders within a practical electrode formulation, C45 was selected as the active carbon material due to its proven performance as both an active material and conductive additive in lithium and potassium ion batteries [29], [30]. Moreover, studies have shown the compatibility of this carbon material with cellulose-derived binders [29], [31].

Figure 6 a and **Figure S1 a** show the results of the GC characterization. As it can be observed, all the materials exhibit excellent cycling stability and specific capacities consistent with values reported in literature for similar systems [32]. Although the four electrodes deliver comparable capacities during the first twenty cycles, clear differences emerge afterwards: the C45/CNC electrodes outperform the C45/CMC electrode, with C45/eN-CNC achieving the highest capacity overall. Remarkably, it should be noted that the commercial C45/CMC electrode exhibits a slight fluctuation in specific capacity between cycles 20th and 45th, while the C45/CNC electrodes show remarkable stability and capacity retention beyond the initial cycles.

Figure 6 b shows the bar graph of the specific discharge capacity fading of each cycle with respect to the previous one, for the first five cycles. The largest irreversible capacity fading takes place between the first and the second cycle, which is attributed to the formation of the SEI layer [33]. However, as shown in the figure, the capacity fading decreases rapidly over the subsequent cycles, resulting in only a minor loss between 1% and 3% at the 5th cycle. The electrode with the highest capacity fading (and therefore the lowest reversibility) is C45/CMC. In contrast, the C45/CNC electrodes demonstrate improved reversibility, with C45/eN-CNC showing the lowest capacity decay from the third cycle on. This trend is further confirmed by the data presented in **Figure S1 b**, which shows capacity retentions at the 100th cycle with respect to the capacity at the 5th cycle. The C45/CMC electrode exhibits the lowest capacity retention (81%), followed by C45/N-CNC and C45/S-CNC (both with 93%), while C45/eN-CNC achieves the highest retention of 97%.

These results can be attributed to differences in surface chemistry and functional groups between CNC and CMC. Neutral CNC produced by enzymatic hydrolysis (eN-CNC) presents a cleaner surface and with minimal surface charges, free from sulfate or other ionic functional groups that could negatively affect electrochemical stability. This neutral **and aggregated** surface minimizes side reactions with the electrolyte and potassium ions, which would otherwise catalyze electrolyte decomposition and degrade the electrode/electrolyte interface. By limiting these undesired

interactions, as done for CNC, stable cycling behavior and reduced capacity fading are more easily achieved.

Figure 6. (a) Galvanostatic cycling performance at 0.05 A/g of half-cells assembled with the four different C45/binder electrodes (excluding the first cycle). (b) Bar graph of specific discharge capacity fading over different cycle numbers for the four different C45/binder electrodes.

The voltage profiles of the C45/binder electrodes during galvanostatic cycling are presented in **Figure 7**. Excluding the first cycle, all profiles exhibit a similar shape characteristic of pseudocapacitive charge storage, marked by the absence of well-defined plateaus [34]. These pseudocapacitive materials store charge through Faradaic processes that predominantly occur at the surface of the electrode rather than within the bulk [34]. This behavior has been previously reported for carbon anodes using C45 as active material, indicating that the use of CNC-based binders does not alter the intrinsic charge storage mechanism [29]. It should also be noticed that, from the second cycle onward, the voltage profiles of all electrodes nearly overlap, indicating excellent cycling stability and minimal occurrence of irreversible reactions.

When comparing the first and second cycles of each electrode, significant differences are observed in both profile shape and specific capacity, mainly attributed to the formation of the SEI during the initial cycle [33]. Notably, in the first cycle, the C45/CNCs electrodes display a voltage plateau around 0.65 V that is absent in the C45/CMC cell, suggesting distinct SEI formation mechanisms depending on the binder employed. This is consistent with previous studies showing that binder selection can influence the starting potential of electrolyte reduction and the composition of the resulting SEI layer [35].

Additionally, it can be observed that the C45/CMC electrode exhibits the highest initial specific discharge capacity (i.e., 468 mAh/g), while the C45/CNCs electrodes show lower capacities ranging

from approximately 250 to 300 mAh/g. However, despite its high initial capacity, the C45/CMC electrode undergoes a sharp capacity drop in the second cycle (as shown in **Figure 6 b**), indicating that much of the first-cycle capacity is associated with irreversible processes. In contrast, the C45/CNC electrodes display more moderate initial capacities, followed by improved reversibility and stable cycling behavior. This kind of achievement is crucial for the development of future potassium-ion full cell, where the K-ion amount is not practically unlimited as in half-cell with potassium metal as anode, but instead in full cell K-ions are limited and it is of vital importance to not waste so many of them in side reactions and decomposition reactions ascribed to the SEI layer formation.

Figure 7. Galvanostatic charge and discharge profiles at different cycle numbers (at 0.05 A/g) for (a) C45/eN-CNC, (b) C45/N-CNC, (c) C45/S-CNC, and (d) C45/CMC.

Figure 8 shows the cyclic voltammograms from the 1st to the 5th cycle for the four different C45/binder electrodes. In the case of the C45/CNC cells, all the three electrodes exhibit very similar electrochemical behavior. During the first reduction scan, a pronounced peak appears at approximately 0.65 V, which correlates with the electrolyte decomposition detected by the plateau in the galvanostatic profiles of **Figure 7** and the CVs peaks of **Figure 5**. This peak has been widely

reported for carbon electrodes with both cellulose-based and PVDF binders and is typically associated with the SEI layer formation [36], [37]. In contrast, the C45/CMC cell also exhibits a signal in this region, although less sharply defined, which is consistent with previous reports [29], [37]. All cells also display a large irreversible slope in the low potential region (0.3–0.01 V) during the first reduction scan, attributed to K^+ intercalation into the carbon matrix [38]. The corresponding first oxidation branch presents a peak located around 0.5 V, which can be related to the K-ion deintercalation process.

From the second cycle onward, all the CV curves exhibit highly reproducible behavior, almost overlapping ones over the others. The reduction branches present two broad peaks. The first one, between 1.3 and 0.5 V, corresponds to the surface-driven redox reactions. The second one, located between 0.5 and 0.01 V, reflects bulk diffusion and insertion of K-ions into the carbon matrix.

Moving on to the oxidation branch, it can be observed that the four C45/binder electrodes exhibit a broad low-potential peak at approximately 0.25 V, which intensifies from the second cycle onward, and a second peak centered at ~ 0.6 V. This dual-peak behavior has been previously reported for C45/CMC electrodes and is attributed to a two-step depotassiation process, involving both bulk ion deintercalation and surface ion release [29].

Figure S2 compares the second CV cycle of each C45/CNC electrode with the same cycle number of each corresponding binder electrode. As shown, the contribution of the binders to the overall current is negligible, confirming that the electrochemical response in the C45/CNC electrodes mainly corresponds to the active carbon material.

Figure 8. CV voltammograms at 0.1 mV/s of the C45/binder electrodes: (a) C45/eN-CNC, (b) C45/N-CNC, (c) C45/S-CNC, and (d) C45/CMC.

EIS measurements were carried out on the C45/binder electrodes during galvanostatic cycling at 0.05 A/g. **Figure 9** shows a comparison of the EIS spectra of the electrodes in three representative states: pristine (a), after one cycle (b), and 100 cycles (c). Each Nyquist plot features a depressed semicircle in the high-to-mid frequency region, attributed to the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and the surface film impedance, followed by a sloped line at low frequencies associated with K-ion diffusion. The semicircle diameter serves as a measure of R_{ct} at the electrode/electrolyte interface. As it can be seen, a remarkable decrease in R_{ct} is observed after cycling, indicating an improvement in charge transfer kinetics likely due to the formation of a stable and more conductive SEI. This trend has previously been reported for carbon anodes in KIBs using KFSI as electrolyte salt [39]. It should be noted that, in all cases, the C45/CNC electrodes exhibit lower R_{ct} values compared to C45/CMC, suggesting that CNC-based binders promote more efficient charge transfer. This behavior indicates that the binders produced from neutral cellulose nanocrystals provide a highly effective physical network that binds carbon particles tightly, enhancing the electrical conductivity while maintaining strong adhesion to

the current collector. The capacity of nanocelluloses to effectively interact with carbon particles, disrupting their aggregates has been already reported in the literature [40], [41].

Figure S3 expands this analysis by showing Nyquist plots at additional cycling stages. The data reveal that the most pronounced decrease in R_{ct} occurs between the pristine state and the first cycle, with only minor changes thereafter. Additionally, the general shape of the impedance spectra does not significantly change after the first cycle, suggesting a stable SEI layer formation and unchanged charge-storage kinetics over extended cycling.

As it can be observed, the depressed semicircle in the pristine electrodes is followed by a nearly vertical line in the low-frequency region. This behavior is typical of fresh electrodes and it is associated with a double-layer capacitance where ions adsorb at the surface without significant intercalation into the bulk [41, 42]. Upon cycling, this profile transitions into a semicircle followed by a line with a slope of approximately 45° , indicative of diffusion-limited processes. This evolution further confirms the formation of a stable SEI layer and the progressive intercalation of K^+ into the carbon matrix, which alters the shape of the impedance response.

Figure 9. Nyquist plots of the EIS measurements for the four C45/binder electrodes after different galvanostatic cycling at 0.05 A/g: (a) pristine electrodes, (b) after the first cycle, and (c) after 100 cycles.

The composition of the electrode binder can significantly influence reaction kinetics, leading to different electrochemical responses [35]. To evaluate this effect, the rate capability of the C45/CNC electrodes was measured, and the results are presented in **Figure S4**. As shown, all electrodes exhibit similar capacity retention across the tested C-rates. It should be noted that, when the current density returns to the lowest value after high-rate cycling, the capacity is fully recovered. This demonstrates the excellent reversibility of the C45/CNC electrodes and underscores the ability of CNC binders to withstand high currents without mechanical degradation. Notably, C45/eN-CNC consistently delivers the highest specific capacity at each current density.

In order to better understand the difference in the electrochemical responses of the C45/CNC electrodes, morphological characterizations of the pristine electrodes were carried out and the results are shown in **Figure 10**. At low magnification (**Figure 10 a-c**), it can be observed that all the electrodes present a fairly homogenous surface with well-distributed active carbon particles and without perceptible agglomerations. However, the C45/N-CNC (**Figure 10 b**) and especially the C45/S-CNC (**Figure 10 c**) electrodes display visible surface cracks, whereas the C45/eN-CNC electrode remains crack-free and appears notably smoother. Looking at the higher magnification micrographs (**Figures 10 d-f**), residual CNC particles are evident on all electrodes, but those on the C45/S-CNC sample are noticeably larger. Such morphological differences likely contribute to the observed variation in the electrochemical performance.

The surface chemistry of the binders could explain these differences among the electrodes morphology. On one hand, the negatively charged sulfate groups on S-CNC may induce electrostatic repulsion with the carbon surface, leading to weaker binder-carbon interaction and facilitating crack formation. On the other hand, neutral cellulose nanocrystals exhibit a homogeneous charge distribution, yielding a more stable surface.

Figure 10. SEM images at two magnification levels of C45/CNCs electrodes: (a) and (d) C45/eN-CNC, (b) and (e) C45/N-CNC, and (c) and (f) C45/S-CNC.

Conclusions

In this study, we have synthesized and characterized three types of cellulose nanocrystals produced via different hydrolysis methods. The mechano-enzymatic approach has revealed higher reaction yield, the formation of cellulose nanocrystals with good purity and crystallinity properties. The high yield makes the mechano-enzymatic approach very competitive with respect to the benchmark

preparation methods based on the use of inorganic acids (sulfuric or hydrochloric acids). Furthermore, we have synthesized both nanocrystals characterized by surface sulfation (S-CNC) and nanocrystals composed of pure cellulose (N-CNC and eN-CNC) and demonstrated that the synthesized CNCs serve as effective, sustainable binder materials for carbon anodes in K-ion batteries. Cyclic voltammetry on bare binder electrodes confirmed that all three CNCs types exhibit excellent electrochemical stability within the 0.01–3 V region vs. K^+/K , with negligible redox activity beyond the initial SEI layer formation. The electrochemical characterizations carried out on CNC-based carbon electrodes prepared with Super C45 evidenced that the C45/CNC electrodes outperform those prepared using conventional carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) as a binder.

Among the CNC variants, C45/eN-CNC electrodes stood out by delivering the highest specific capacities, best capacity retention (97% after 100 cycles), and the most homogeneous electrode surface. This superior performance is attributed to its neutral surface chemistry, which minimizes undesired side reactions and enables the formation of a stable SEI. N-CNC and S-CNC also outperformed CMC in terms of cyclability and impedance, though S-CNC ionic surface groups led to slight mechanical irregularities. Overall, our findings underscore the promise of CNCs—particularly enzymatically produced, neutral nanocrystals—as green, cost-effective alternatives to both PVDF and conventional cellulose derivatives for potassium-ion battery electrodes.

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